

Table S5. Genes assessed by PCR

Gene	TaqMan Assay ID	Dye-Probe	Supplier	Catalogue number
FOXJ1	Hs00201755_m1	FAM-MGB	ThermoFisher Scientific	4331182
SPDEF	Hs0017942_m1	FAM-MGB	ThermoFisher Scientific	4331182
SCGB1	Hs00171092_m1	FAM-MGB	ThermoFisher Scientific	4331182
18s	N/A	VIC-MGB	ThermoFisher Scientific	4319413E